

FUNCTIONS OF DEVELOPING DEONTOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Annotation. The article discusses the level of deontological competence of future teachers of education in the process of higher education and the methods and means of its development. The structural structure of the functions of developing deontological competence in future teachers of education and the possibility of achieving results through their implementation are highlighted.

Keywords: deontological competence, pedagogical deontology, educational process, ethics, competence, responsibility, socialization, value, function.

Today, the reform and improvement of the continuous education system of our country, which is moving towards independent development, raising it to a new level of quality, as well as increasing the efficiency of education through the training of highly qualified specialists in their profession, has become a state policy. One of the urgent issues of today is the formation and development of deontological competence in future teachers studying in our country, along with education, appropriate to their profession, and the widespread use of all opportunities to educate the younger generation as well-rounded individuals. Therefore, the main task of today's higher education is to prepare future teachers of the discipline of education for innovative activities in accordance with the requirements of the time, as well as to form in them a deep understanding of deontological duty and the ability to comply with it, to ensure that future teachers have sufficient competence, and to improve and develop their knowledge and skills. It is impossible to achieve success in the educational process if the teacher is not perfect and experienced. Therefore, it is precisely for today's teachers to be mature specialists that the development of any field is based.

The concept of forming the deontological culture of a future teacher of education is aimed at the principles of cooperation between teachers and students, joint effective work, and the development of deontological competence of a future teacher in the future. The requirement is that the deontological and professional competence of future teachers of education studying in higher education today must fully meet the requirements of world standards and the state educational standards of Uzbekistan. Today's teacher should be a creative, enterprising, selfless performer of his profession, a mature example of decency and morality, communicative, creative, able to correctly respond to the problem and use effective methods and tools on this basis, and faithfully approach his duty. Today, a specialist working in any field acquires basic knowledge and skills in the school process. A student who does not receive a good education at school cannot master higher education well, as a result, cadres who cannot perform their profession well are produced, which is why teachers teaching at school must be qualified specialists. This allows for progress and development not only in education, but also in all areas. Today's teacher should organize his professional activities on the basis of deontological requirements and, based on the development of his existing

competence, should focus on the upbringing of a harmonious generation. A high level of understanding and implementation of the duty of a teacher regulates the actions of the teacher and governs his rights. The following can be included in the methods for developing deontological competence in future teachers of the discipline of education:

1) by type of cognitive activity: explanatory-illustrative; reproductive; problematic presentation of the material; partial-exploratory; research;

2) active methods: heuristic conversation; educational discussion; independent work with literature; imitation of professional activity;

3) on the analysis of situations: event educational technology, randomness; brainstorming; situational; problematic; social pedagogical design.

Through the above methods, future teachers in the education system are trained. Today, not only in our country, but also all over the world, attention has been paid to the field of education, and the main issue for the development of education is, first of all, the training of qualified personnel, the production of excellent specialists in their profession. All over the world, a number of scientific researches are being conducted to develop deontological competence as an important component of the professional training of future teachers, to identify its didactic aspects, and to improve the pedagogical mechanism for the development of methodological knowledge as the basis for innovative activities.

The development of deontological competence in future teachers can be achieved by implementing the following functions. These are

1. Ethical-pedagogical: understanding and studying the ethical orientation of the pedagogical vision in the system of "man - society" and "man - man" and the deontological mission of the teacher in the world of various cultures;

2. Ethnopedagogical: involves the teacher's perception of the ethnocultural (material and spiritual) mentality reflected in the historical experience and the role of the ethnos as a transmitter of a particular language in the evolutionary development of humanity;

3. Communicative: the purpose of pedagogical activity expresses the need for the future teacher to master various communicative technologies of joint actions with students in accordance with the principles of pedagogical deontology;

4. Educational: arises as a component of the teacher's professional activity and is carried out through continuous professional development and self-education in accordance with the principles of pedagogical duty and pedagogical deontology.

In conclusion, it should be said that the deontological competence of a future teacher of education is combined with the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for his professional activity, his pedagogical authority, functional, that is, the ability to put professional knowledge and skills into practice, the ability to think analytically and take a complex approach to performing his duties, the ability to adapt to different situations, the ability to have social, communicative, and integrative skills, and the ability to find a common language in any team. In this case, the deontological image of a future teacher of education includes:

- being cultured;
- possessing universal human values;
- possessing national culture;
- participating in the social life of the country;
- respect for the culture of other nations, -

- possession of skills such as the experience of having a positive emotional attitude towards society, people, and nature is one of the main structural elements.

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